

Role of Education in Women Empowerment

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Education is the most important tool for Women Empowerment

Education is a potent tool in the emancipation and empowerment of women. The greatest single factor which can incredibly improve the status of women in any society is Education. It is indispensable that education enables women not only to gain more knowledge about the world outside of her hearth and home but helps her to get status, positive self esteem and confidence, necessary courage and inner strength to face challenges in life. Apparently it also facilitates them to procure a job and supplement the income of family and achieve social status. Education especially of women has a major impact on health and nutrition as an instrument of developing a sustainable strategy for population control. Moreover, educated women can play an equally important role as men in nation building. Thus there is no denying fact that education empowers women. Indeed the different organs of the United Nations and experts on women's liberation argue for women's education as the basic step to attain equality with men.

In spite of the sincere efforts by the State and Central Governments through various schemes and programmes over the last 62 years and above all, the United Nation's enormous pressure with regard to the uplift of the plight of women in terms education is still in the state of an enigma in India for several reasons. The 2001 Census report indicates that literacy among women as only 54 %. The growth of women's education in the rural area is very slow. This obviously means that still a large women folk of our country are illiterate, weak, backward and exploited. Moreover, education is also not available to all equally. Gender inequality is reinforced in education which is proved by the fact that the literacy rate for women is only 54 % against 76 % of men as per 2001 census.

The present paper tries to find the root causes for low literacy among women in India as well as to provide remedial measures for improving the literacy level of women in our country.

VARIOUS CAUSES FOR LOW LITERACY

Women education is a multi-dimensional phenomenon. No single factor or cause can be held responsible for very low literacy rate of women in India. Subsequently it is associated with combination of many factors including social, cultural, economic, educational, demographic, political and administrative and so on. The following are the some of the important factors which could be attributed for the present poor state of affairs of womenfolk in education.

Poor Enrolment:

Poor enrolment of girls in schools is one of the foundational factors which stand as stumbling block for women empowerment in India. Reliable sources indicate that more than 50 % of the Non-Starters (those who have never been to school) are girls.

Higher drop-out:

The drop –outs among girls especially in rural, tribal and slums areas seem to be quite high. According to available sources, occurrence of drop-out and stagnation amongst girls is nearly twice that of boys all over India

Girl Child plays the role of Mother at Home:

In many families especially in urban slums, girls play the role of second mother by taking the responsibilities of household work such as looking after the sibling, fetching water, bringing fodder for cattle, cleaning and cooking etc. In rural India especially in poor families this traditional sex role discourages girl child to go school as it becomes secondary

Cast System as a Barrier:

Children belonging to low caste families are forced to learn skills and work ways and not encouraged to go to school due to various factors in the sphere of strict instruction /threat from high caste communities for their selfish motives of keeping them as domestic servants and child labourers in the farms or factory.

Dowry as cordon:

Dowry system and other social practices act as main causes of the neglect of the girl child and discrimination against girl child including the deprivation of right of education. In many families especially poor and down-trodden think that if their daughters are educated more, they have to accumulate more assets and properties to provide as dowry in large proportion at the time of marriage, so prefer rather to either stop their children with average education and so on but never higher education. This prevails more in underprivileged families and communities where some people used to kill their young daughters because they could not arrange dowry for their marriage.

More work less payment:

Most of the industries in India prefer girl children for high productivity and low cost.

Poor School Environment for girls:

In general the school environment for girls in India is not really interesting and encouraging. The subjects taught in schools are also not related to the environment of girl children. The methods of teaching are mostly out – dated, rigid and uninteresting. There are still hundreds of

schools with poor basic amenities such as drinking water, latrine and toilet facilities, improper building, and inadequate number of teachers' especially female teachers preferable for any parents for safety of their girl children from different types of exploitation and abuse.

Early age of marriage:

There is high association of female literacy with female age at marriage. By and large the female age at marriage of 18 (recently 21 years) as prescribed by various legislations not at all followed in India. It is very much ignored and neglected by the families of parents with low literacy and illiteracy background. This obnoxious practice discourages female children to continue their schooling and higher education as they enter into family life at the early age which is not advisable from the physical and mental health point of view and also of social development.

Poverty:

In much poverty stricken families, children especially girls are considered as economic assets as they bring income for livelihood as well to save from economic crises due to death or incapacity of parents (sick/ handicapped/aged)

Ineffective Law Enforcing Machinery:

Indian constitution and various legislations pertaining to education to children assure free and compulsory education all children of this nation but unfortunately the enforcement machinery fail to discharge its duties and responsibilities to the satisfaction of the public interest and welfare of women

Demographic Factors:

The high population growth rate, rapid urbanization, migration etc also attribute immensely for the poor literacy level of women and girls in India

Lack of Political Will and Conviction:

Government officials, policy makers, politicians etc of our country have neither political will nor conviction for the empowerment of women in general.

SOME MEASURES FOR IMPROVING THE LITERACY LEVEL OF WOMEN IN INDIA

Following measures can be considered for improving the literacy level of Women in India

- Efforts must be initiated jointly by the government, parents and civil society to achieve universal enrolment for girls without any compromise. The enrolment can be made even mandatory for every girl by the government in the realm of compulsory education.

- Education Ministry both at Centre and State level should come together and stop the ongoing high drop-outs among girls especially in rural, tribal and slums areas with the serious involvement of voluntary organizations.
- The poverty stricken families can be identified through proper research and necessary poverty alleviation services be provided to strengthen the income thereby to enable the families to send their children to schools and colleges without much financial difficulties
- Bonded Child labour and Child labour practice must be abolished with strict administrative measures and the relieved children from bondage should be integrated into schools with suitable defence social mechanism.
- Appropriate steps should be taken by the educational authorities with the participation of communities in order to bring the girl children to the main stream of education and development at every level including family and community.
- The female child in every Indian family irrespective of socio-economic status should be molded to overcome the challenges of inferiority; subservience and domesticity which place sever limitations on her education and development. Every family irrespective its socio-cultural and economic background can take it a challenge to bring up their girl children as dignified human being with empowerment in physical, mental, economic and social dimensions of life.
- The Midday meal scheme and other educational supportive services like free text books, Note books , Fee uniforms , Free Bicycles, Free bus , scholarships Free bus pass and so on as done in the state of Tamil Nadu can be provided in all states and union territories to lift up the literacy level among girls
- As social evils like dowry, child marriage , caste system and other practices deprive rights of education for children belonging to poor and underprivileged families and communities, they should eliminated through well-designed packages of mass awareness programmes and social welfare measures with full support of public, political parties, NGOs and government agencies.
- The electronic and print media can play significant role in building a good and positive image about girls and women in general in the society by giving no focus for such advertisements and news fetching commercial gain at the cost of depicting women as an object. This would help in changing the society's attitudes towards girls and their roles to treat every girl or woman as human being with self respect and dignity.
- Government, voluntary sector and philanthropic organizations and individuals should come forward to provide free education for poor girls and provide free hostel facilities for girls studying in schools and colleges in every state of India. This will certainly encourage children of poor families to pursue good and higher education without much impediments.
- The schools of social work, departments of women studies, Women Universities and other educational institutions in hand with NGOs and social service organizations such as Rotary

Clubs , Lions Clubs , women lib organizations associations can work together to improve the educational status of the womenfolk in this country on mutual respect and understanding.

- The parents of children belonging to poor, underprivileged families must be specially educated with proper social formula to help them to understand the significance of education for their girl children as foundation for empowerment
- Government, NGOs and public should work hand in hand to implement the minimum age at marriage (21 and above) Awareness should be created to institutionalize it as a traditional practice cut crossing castes, religions, community etc.
- Government officials, policy makers, political parties and others should have adequate political will and conviction to empower women in India without double standard mind
- The law enforcing machinery should be made really effective with efficient monitoring vigilant system to implement the constitutional and legislative provisions and administrative measures to assure free and compulsory education for all children of this nation without any gender discrimination.

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